

Readme for the DCC2GO training compendium

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1 Introduction to the DCC2GO training compendium

Replacement of paper-based calibration certificates by digital counterparts Digital Calibration Certificates (DCCs) is vital for the digital transformation of many European industrial and legal metrology sectors. However, not all members of the European metrology community have access to the knowledge and capabilities needed for the implementation of DCCs. The small collaborative project EMPIR 21SCP01 DCC2GO has addressed this issue by supporting the implementation of DCCs within the European metrology community through the coordinated production and sharing of training material (DCC2GO, 2022).

1.1 Aim

The DCC2GO training compendium can be used by stakeholders with no prior knowledge of DCCs to gain basic knowledge on DCCs. The DCC training compendium will be suitable for a wide range of stakeholders with particular focus on the community of small and emerging National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated Institutes (DIs). It aims to support a harmonised level of DCC knowledge within the European metrology community. A collection of hands-on examples and guidelines to start working with DCCs (DCC Starter-Kit) accompanies the material produced by DCC2GO (D. Baslev-Harder, 2023).

1.2 Concept

The DCC2GO training compendium includes an overview on the current state-of-the-art of DCC development and usage. It covers a range of information, from the basic properties and advantages of DCCs for NMIs, DIs and their stakeholders, to full technical specifications for metrology practitioners and technical support (e.g., IT information), to overview documents for senior management and other stakeholder organisations in the metrology community. The DCC training compendium will also categorise DCCs currently in use or in development in

terms of different types of functionalities and application areas, as well as their benefits and requirements. This categorisation should enable providers and users of calibrations to decide which types of DCCs are the most feasible and appropriate for specific use cases. The relevance of the materials supporting the knowledge on DCCs was evaluated through a survey across users and reviewed by members of the DCC2GO project and EURAMET TC-IM 1448 project members (EURAMET, 2018).

2 DCC2GO training compendium

2.1 Overview on DCC types

DCC2GO has identified five different types of DCC:

- Type 0
A DCC is provided as an electronic file which enables a simple digitisation of processes. The DCC data is only human-readable. Examples are formats such as PDF files, Word documents, or spreadsheets that are, in many cases, already in use today to exchange calibration certificates.
- Type 1
A DCC is provided as an electronic file that is human-readable and has an additional machine-readable appendix. An example implementation is the PDF/A-3 file with attached machine-readable data that is structured, for example, in Extensive Markup Language (XML) syntax or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) syntax (Gregor Boschung, 2021).
- Type 2
A DCC is provided as a machine-readable electronic file that has a human-readable appendix. An example implementation is the XML DCC format where a human-readable PDF or HTML files can be appended (Siegfried Hackel, 2021).
- Type 3
A DCC is purely provided as a machine-readable electronic file. A human-readable representation of the calibration data is no more part of the file but created from the machine-readable content on-premise. An example is an XML DCC file without the human readable appendix.
- Type 'future vision'
The 'future vision' format removes the limitation of a DCC to be a single file for data exchange. The outcome of a calibration result, its data, and metadata can be distributed across different databases provided by calibration laboratories, metrology organisations, standardisation bodies, and other participants in a digitalised quality infrastructure (Sascha Eichstädt, 2022). Early examples are the provision of common terms in calibration in a dedicated controlled vocabulary database (Benjamin Gloger, 2022) and BIPM's CMC data that can be interlinked between a DCC and the Key Comparison Database by a persistent ID (BIPM, QUICK START: CMC UNIQUE IDENTIFIERS (CMC PIDS), 2023).

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The type classification is not a ranking of different DCC implementations. Depending on the user's needs and the status of the digital transformation of services, the types have different relevance. A simple overview of state-of-the-art advantages and disadvantages depending on different purposes of applications is outlined in Table 1. Many organisations that can already use PDF certificates have identified type 1 as an easy starting point for a transition towards machine-readable formats such as type 2 and type 3. Furthermore, a survey made by the BIPM in 2022 across the consultative committees has found that the international awareness for the XML DCC is significantly high (BIPM, Report on the 2022 survey of CC participants, 2023). This finding is also reflected when looking at the programmes of international conferences such as the IMEKO TC6 M4Dconf2022 on digital transformation (Jon Bartholomew, 2023) and the 3rd International DCC conference (Al Mamun et al, 2023), where most of the presentations on DCCs considered the use of XML. Against this background, the DCC2GO training compendium and starter kit outline examples for PDF/A-3 and XML DCCs.

Table 1 Properties of different DCC types

Property	Type 0	Type 1	Type 2	Type 3	Type 'future vision'
Paper reduction			++		
Increasing efficiency of processes	+	++	++	++	++
Can provide more information to customer		++	++	++	++
Capability of human readability	++	++	++	+	+
Reduce transcription error and exchange time	-	+	++	++	++
Better machine-interoperable content supporting advanced digitalization	-	+	+	+	++

2.2 Material and description

The training compendium consists of several sets of slides explaining the DCC to technical experts, management, and stakeholders of metrology organisations. The material is available for download for self-study. In addition, recordings of presentations of the slides are available online at the DCC2GO webpage (DCC2GO, 2022). The recordings include English subtitles.

In addition, the entry point for initiating work with DCCs is facilitated by the inclusion of guidelines and materials offered in the DCC2GO starter kit. All materials, their descriptions, and recommendations for how to access them are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Materials that from the DCC2GO training compendium

#	Document Description/Access	Target group
1	Readme for the DCC2GO training compendium The readme provides an overview of the materials made available for training on DCCs by the DCC2GO project and the target audience for whom they are intended. <i>DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199281</i>	all
2	Common information on Digital calibration Certificate This set of slides builds the entry point for the training on DCCs for all members of NMIs, Dis, and their stakeholders. It provides basic information such as a definition of the meaning of DCCs, their benefits, and the initial aspects of starting to work with them. <i>Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199281</i>	all
3	Information for management at NMIs and Dis This material comprises slides providing more details on DCCs from a management point of view. It discusses legal and regulatory aspects, as well as information on DCC harmonisation and phases for DCC implementation in an organisation. It is recommended to study material 2 (common information) before reading this material. <i>Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199281</i>	management
4	Information for technical staff at NMIs and Dis This material for technical staff members working with DCCs provides a deep dive into the DCC implementation examples using the PDF/A-3 format and the XML format. The creation and use of DCCs are discussed in front of the lifecycle of measuring equipment and calibration services. The material contains information on early work with DCCs, advanced developments, and examples of IT requirements. It is recommended to study material 2 (common information) before reading this material. Material 6 (example for DCC creation) is suitable follow-on material to the technical information. <i>Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199281</i>	technical experts
5	Information for stakeholders This material comprises slides that summarise the impact of DCCs aiming at stakeholders of NMIs and Dis. It includes the outline of the Proof-of-Concept implementation of DCCs in a calibration chain demonstrating the link across an NMI, accredited calibration laboratory and an end-user of calibration. It is recommended to study material 2 (common information) before reading this material. <i>Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199281</i>	stakeholders
6	Example for the creation of a Digital Calibration Certificate (DCC) in XML and PDF/A-3 for people who start working with DCCs This suite of slides, data, and software provides an easy-to-follow step-by-step guideline allowing users to create and explore their first XML DCC and PDF/A-3 DCC examples based on temperature calibration data. It demonstrates a quick (and dirty) approach based on open-access software tools. It is recommended to study material 1 (common information) and 2 (technical information) before continuing to go through this example. <i>Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199718</i>	technical experts
7	Freely available and validated, Digital Calibration Certificates (DCC) starter kit for DCC implementation; containing step-by-step guidance for the creation, practical implementation and secure delivery of temperature and pressure DCCs See Section 4 for further description. The starter kit includes guidelines with blueprints for further implementation of DCCs, extending the basic knowledge from material 3 (management information) and material 4 (technical information). Furthermore, it provides a comprehensive list of additional examples and tools available for working with DCCs. <i>Access DOI 10.5281/zenodo.8199700</i>	all

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3 DCC2GO starter kit

The DCC2GO starter kit consists of practical guidance for metrology institutes to enable them to start working with DCCs (D. Baslev-Harder, 2023). It contains step-by-step guidance for the creation, practical implementation, and secure delivery of DCCs. Blueprints for workflows to introduce DCCs at an organisation have been established. These workflows combine the experience obtained by the DCC2GO project members, which are all European metrology organisations that have gone through the process of introducing DCCs in the past years. The DCC starter kit is a suite of guidelines containing the following documents:

Guideline 1

How Metrology Institutes can start working with DCCs without any prior knowledge

This guideline addresses such issues as how to create a DCC, what IT infrastructure is needed and how to deal with the IT tools for handling the DCC.

Guideline 2

Collation of cryptographic tool information for DCC protection and validation

This guideline focuses on aspects of protection and secure submission of DCCs. It comprises different types of mechanisms for securing the content of DCCs such as digital signatures.

Table of DCC related resources

This table provides a broader collection of tools and documentation for DCCs that is openly available today. Background information is provided to users who start working with DCCs to allow faster access to relevant tools and information beyond the basic knowledge and training from DCC2GO.

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6 Common Abbreviations

BIPM	International Bureau of Weight and Measures
DCC	Digital Certificate of Calibration
DI	Designated Institute
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object notation
NMI	National Metrology Institute
PID	Persistent Identifier
TC-IM	Technical Committee on Interdisciplinary Metrology
XML	eXtensive Markup Language

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